

Comparison of urban green classification methods using Quickbird, Ikonos and Worldview-2 imagery

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Abstract: The objective of this research work is two-fold: first to compare Worldview-2, IKONOS and Quickbird imagery with respect to urban green classification (the evergreen and deciduous trees) in two central urban parks in Thessaloniki, Greece, and second to obtain the best accuracy in matching the pixel-level with the object-based classifications. Representative classification algorithms, such as Maximum Likelihood classification and Decision Tree algorithm, were tested at the pixel level, and in the classification process the indices of Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Modified Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (MSAVI) and Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) were computed on the images. The available normalized Digital Surface Model (nDSM) of the study areas improved even more the classification results. For the evaluation of the resulted classified images statistical tests were applied, and the results suggested that the developed classification system using NDVI and nDSM achieved the highest accuracy in comparison to traditional pixel-based classification methods, whereas object-oriented classification through the Decision Tree algorithm gave better accuracy results than other methods.

Keywords: Remote Sensing, Vegetation, Land Cover

1. Introduction

High spatial resolution images have been increasingly used for urban land classification. Urban green trees provide shade for buildings, lower the ambient air temperature in hot weather and reduce the concentrations of atmospheric pollutants. This project compares the results of an object-oriented classification to a supervised pixel-based classification for identifying urban green classification (the evergreen and deciduous trees) in two central parks of Thessaloniki (Y.M.CA. park and Pedion tou Areos park).

2. The data used

For the purpose of this study three satellite data were used: one pan-sharpened WorldView-2 image, dated February 2010, with spatial resolution of 0.50m, one pan-sharpened Ikonos image, dated July 2006, with spatial resolution of 1m, and one pan-sharpened Quickbird image of July 2003, with spatial resolution of 0.7m.

Additionally, elevation data was used, consisting of a normalised Digital Surface Model (nDSM= DSM – DTM) with a 1-m grid size.

Furthermore, in order to assess the classification procedures, field surveys were conducted in the two examined central parks of Thessaloniki on February 19 of 2012. The position of every tree was acquired using the GMS-2 GPS. Ground truth data for various types of trees were acquired for the validation processes.

3. Methodology

In this study six supervised classification procedures were applied on the three satellite images: three methods using traditional per-pixel approach with maximum likelihood algorithm and three methods of object-oriented classifications using rule based hierarchy models and Decision Trees. The same classes were selected for every classification process; in type and in number. Maximum likelihood procedure is based on Bayesian probability theory. It uses information from a set of training sites to estimate the posterior probability that a pixel belongs to each class.

Additionally, the indices of Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Modified Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (MSAVI) and Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) were computed in order to achieve better results.

In detail, the six classification methodologies that were applied on the three images are the following:

1. Maximum Likelihood Supervised Classification using the available bands of the images
2. Maximum Likelihood Supervised Classification using the available bands of the images and the derived NDVI image for each satellite
3. Maximum Likelihood Supervised Classification using the available bands of the images, the derived NDVI and the available nDSM
4. Object oriented classification using multy resolution segmentation, based on rule-based hierarchy model that takes into consideration the spectral, as well as the geometrical characteristics of the segmented objects
5. Pixel based Classification using a Decision tree with various rules based on spectral values of the images
6. Object oriented Classification using a Decision tree with various rules based on spectral values of the images

In this research Erdas Imagine 9.2, eCognition Developer 8.7 and ENVI 4.4. were used for image processing.

4. Accuracy assessment for the applied methodologies

After completing all the classification methodologies the accuracy evaluation was carried out based on ground truth data from the field investigation. The accuracy statistics of the applied methods on the three satellite images are presented in Table 1, 2 and 3.

Comparing the classification accuracies between using segmentation-based mean-spectral images and using per-pixel spectral-based multispectral images, it is revealed that that segmentation-based method has significantly improved the classification performance for all land covers. On the other hand, the overall accuracy of Maximum likelihood Classification using NDVI and nDSM as additional bands as well as the per pixel classification using a Decision tree was 100%.

Table 1. Accuracy results for Quickbird

Quickbird Test Case Studies				
Pedion tou Areos park			Y.M.CA. park	
	Overall accuracy	Overall kappa statistics	Overall accuracy	Overall kappa statistics
Maximum likelihood Classification				
Satellite Image (4bands)	100%	1	96.30%	0.8916
Satellite Image +NDVI	100%	1.0000	100%	1.0000
Satellite Image +NDVI+ nDSM	100%	1.0000	100.00%	1.0000
Object-oriented classification	100%	1	100.00%	1
Decision Tree _{pixel}	100%	1	94.74%	0.8995
Decision Tree _{Object}	100%	1	100.00%	1

Table 2. Accuracy results for Ikonos

IKONOS Test Case Studies				
Pedion tou Areos park			Y.M.CA. park	
	Overall accuracy	Overall kappa statistics	Overall accuracy	Overall kappa statistics
Maximum likelihood Classification				
Satellite Image (4bands)	80.00%	0.5	92.59%	0.6805
Satellite Image +NDVI	90.00%	0.7368	80.00%	0.6364
Satellite Image +nDSM +NDVI	90.00%	0.7368	90.00%	0.8000
Object-oriented classification	87.50	0.7143	96.67%	0.933
Decision Tree _{pixel}	100.00%	1	87.50	0.7647
Decision Tree _{Object}	100.00%	1	91.67%	0.8462

Table3. Accuracy results for Worldview-2

Worldview-2 Test Case Studies				
Pedion tou Areos park			Y.M.CA. park	
	Overall accuracy	Overall kappa statistics	Overall accuracy	Overall kappa statistics
Maximum likelihood Classification				
Satellite Image (8bands)	80.00%	0.6970	85.19%	0.7195
Satellite Image (4bands)	60%	0.4118	70.00%	0.5313
Satellite Image +nDSM +NDVI ₁	100.00%	1.0000	90.00%	0.7826
Satellite Image +nDSM +NDVI ₂	100.00%	1.0000	90.00%	0.8305
Object-oriented classification	90%	0.8387	90.00%	0.7964
Decision Tree _{pixel}	88.89%	0.7750	100%	1
Decision Tree _{Object}	100%	1	100%	1

5. Conclusions

The aim of the presented paper was to classify effectively vegetated area within the residential area of Thessaloniki. The best methodology according to average accuracy values was Maximum Likelihood Algorithm and per pixel classification using a Decision Tree on QuickBird image data.

Comparing the classification accuracies between segmentation-based mean-spectral images and per-pixel spectral-based multispectral images, it is indicated that segmentation-based method significantly improved classification performance.

Once we acquire NDVI images throughout the year, we should be able to classify different vegetation types (Deciduous –Evergreen). Additionally, the use of nDSM and NDVI could give the best accuracy.

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References